

Nitrogen Ligated Nickel (II) Complexes

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Methods of preparation of the complexes of the types NiL_4X_2 , where L=pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, aniline and benzylamine, $X=ClO_3^-$ for pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline and $X=Cl'$, Br' and I' for aniline and benzylamine, NiL_2X_4 , where L=aniline, piperidine, isoquinoline and *o*-toluidine, $X=Cl'$, Br' and I' and $NiLX_3$ where L=quinaldine when X is Cl' and L=pyridine when $X=NCS'$, have been described and from their conductivity, magnetic and spectral studies the complexes have been characterized.

In a previous communication, thermal decomposition studies of the prepared nickel complexes of the types NiL_4X_2 (where L=pyridine, β - and γ picolines, benzylamine and aniline; $X=Cl'$, Br', I', NCS' and ClO_3^-) and NiL_2X_4 (where L=pyridine, α -, β - and γ -picolines, piperidine, quinoline, isoquinoline, *o*-toluidine and aniline and $X=Cl'$, Br' and I') and the isolation of few new compounds of type NiL_4Cl_2 (where I=pyridine, β -picoline and aniline) and $NiLX_3$ (where L=pyridine when X is Cl' and NCS' , and β - and γ -picolines, quinoline when X is Cl') were described¹. It was reported that the methods of this preparation and other properties would be described in a later publication. But subsequently a number of papers²⁻⁸ describing magnetic and spectral properties of some of those compounds reported by us have been published. These findings being in accord with those of ours, in this paper we are simply reporting the properties of those compounds which have not been studied as yet.

The compounds are of three types, NiL_4X_2 (where L=pyridine, β -, γ -picolines, when X is ClO_3^- and L=aniline and benzylamine when $X=Cl'$, Br' and I'), NiL_2X_4 (where L=aniline, piperidine, isoquinoline and *o*-toluidine when X is Cl', Br' or I') and $NiLX_3$ (where L=quinaldine when X is Cl' and L=pyridine when X is NCS'). Table I reports the colour, magnetic moment and the conductivity of these compounds along with those of the tetra-aniline complexes; magnetic values of the latter complexes have not yet been described.⁹ The magnetic moments of all the complexes are in the range of 2.78 to 3.37 B.M., except in the case of Ni(Quinal) Cl_2 , where the value is a bit high, 3.55 B.M. These values are as expected for octahedral Nickel (II) complexes.

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TABLE I

Magnetic moment, colour and conductivity of the complexes

Complex	Colour	λ_m in PhNO ₂ (10 ⁻² M)	Magnetic moment in B. M.
Ni (Py) ₄ (ClO ₃) ₂	Pale blue	3.3	2.95
Ni (β -pic) ₄ (ClO ₃) ₂	Blue	3.4	3.04
Ni (γ -pic) ₄ (ClO ₃) ₂	Blue	3.5	3.04
Ni (An) ₄ Cl ₂	Grey	Insol	3.18
Ni (An) ₄ Br ₂	Pale blue	Insol.	2.78
Ni (An) ₄ I ₂	Pale blue	Insol.	2.82
Ni (Benz) ₄ Cl ₂	Pale blue	Insol.	2.83
Ni (Benz) ₄ Br ₂	Pale blue	Insol	2.85
Ni (Benz) ₄ I ₂	Pale blue	Insol	2.84
Ni (An) ₂ Cl ₂	Light yellow	—	3.37
Ni (Pip) ₂ Cl ₂	Pale green	Insol	3.15
Ni (Pip) ₂ Br ₂	Green	Insol.	2.82
Ni (Pip) ₂ I ₂	Yellowish green	Insol.	2.80
Ni (I-Quin) ₂ Br ₂	Light blue	3.3	—
Ni (I-Quin) ₂ I ₂	Greenish yellow	Decomp.	2.87
Ni (O.T) ₂ Cl ₂	Green	Insol.	2.85
Ni (O.T) ₂ Br ₂	Yellow	3.2	2.84
Ni (O.T) ₂ I ₂	Yellow	Decomp.	2.88
Ni (Py) (ONS) ₂	Yellow	—	3.02
Ni (Quinal) ₂ Cl ₂	Yellow	Insol.	3.55

N.B. Py=Pyridine; β -pic= β -picoline; γ -pic= γ -picoline;
 An=Aniline; Benz=Benzyamine; Pip=Piperidine;
 I-Quin=Isoquinoline; O.T.=Ortho-toluidine; Quinal=Quinaldine.

The solution spectra of the soluble complexes and the reflectance spectra of the insoluble or the very feebly soluble ones have been given in Table II. The absorption maxima of all the complexes appear in three distinct regions, i.e., 27,030-21,740 cm⁻¹; 20,000-13,160 cm⁻¹; 11,910-9,700 cm⁻¹; except in Ni(I-Quin)₂Cl₂, where there is another extra band at 12,990 cm⁻¹. Moreover, in solutions, the band intensities are extremely low. The shortest wavelength band may be assigned as ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P) transition, that at 20,000-13,160 cm⁻¹ is due to ³A_{1g} → ³T_{2g} (F) transition and the lowest frequency band arises due to ³A_{1g} → ³T_{2g} (F) transition. In the case of Ni(I-Quin)₂Cl₂, the extra band which appears at 12,990 cm⁻¹, may be due to ³A_{2g} → ¹E_g (D) transition. So it can be said from the magnetic moment values, absorption maxima and the band intensities that these complexes are all octahedral. Anions may, therefore, take part in coordination. This is borne out by the fact that most of these complexes are either sparingly or feebly soluble in polar solvents. Even those which are slightly more soluble give low conductivity as measured in nitrobenzene. The lesser solubility favours polymeric nature of the complexes with octahedral disposition.

It has been observed^{9,10} that due to tetragonal distortion in many of the compounds of this type, the ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) transition splits to two components. In these octahedral complexes with unsymmetrical ligand field strength such splitting is expected. But due to the limitation of our spectrophotometer which can measure only up to 1000 m μ , the low

energy component of the splitted band could not be detected and as such the field strength of the ligands could not be compared.

TABLE II

Electronic absorption spectra of the complexes

Complex	State	Absorption max (cm ⁻¹) (λ _{max} for soln.)
Ni (Py) ₂ (ClO ₃) ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	26,310(4.6); 20,000(3.6); 10,990(3.1).
Ni (β-Pic) ₂ (ClO ₃) ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	25,000 (4.4); 19,230 (3.8); 10,990 (3.1).
Ni (γ-Pic) ₂ (ClO ₃) ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	25,000 (4.4); 19,230(3.8); 10,990(2.5).
*Ni (Benz) ₂ Cl ₂	Solid (Reflectance)	23,770; 15,300; ~ 9,804(Sh).
Ni (l-Quin) ₂ Cl ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	22,220 (5.8); 18,520 (4.8); 12,990(0.9); 11,910 (0.6).
Ni (l-Quin) ₂ Br ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	24,390 (3.7); 19,610 (2.4); 10,750(1.7).
Ni (l-Quin) ₂ I ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	21,740 (5.0); 17,540(4.6); 10,640 (2.8).
*Ni (O.T) ₂ Br ₂	Solid (Reflectance)	27,030; 16,810; ~ 11,360.
Ni (O.T) ₂ I ₂	CHCl ₃ Soln.	26,310(6.0); 20,000 (7.0); 10,990 (5.0).
*Ni (Pip) ₂ Br ₂	Solid (Reflectance)	~ 26,310; ~ 14,290 (Sh)
*Ni (Py) (CNS) ₂	Solid (Reflectance)	26,310; 15,630; 9,709.
*Ni (Quinal) Cl ₂	Solid (Reflectance)	22,470; 13,160; 11,620.

Of the NiL₂X₂ type complexes isolated¹, Ni(Py) (CNS)₂ and Ni (Quinal) Cl₂, which have been characterised, appear also to be octahedral. Their magnetic values and reflectance spectra are in agreement with other octahedral complexes of their type. Monoquinaldino-bromo- and -iodo-complexes, having light blue and green colour, respectively, are found to be very unstable and ferromagnetic.

EXPERIMENTAL

The nickel bromide and iodide used were prepared by treating nickel carbonate with hydrobromic and hydroiodic acids, respectively. The excess acid was removed by evaporation with alcohol.

Nickel chloride used was hexahydrated, except where specifically mentioned.

Methods of preparation of the complexes are given below. Their analytical results, except that of monoquinaldine nickel chloride, were reported earlier¹.

Preparation of the complexes.

Complexes of the type NiL₂X₂.—The compounds of this type were prepared by adding respective ligand (6 moles) to a solution of nickel halide (1 mole) in ethanol. The crystals separated on cooling were filtered, washed with ethanol containing a small amount of the ligand, dried over anhyd. calcium chloride and analysed.

The chlorate complexes with L=pyridine, β - and γ -picolines were prepared by adding potassium chlorate and the corresponding ligand (6 moles) in water to a solution of nickel nitrate (1 mole). The crystals, which separated immediately, were filtered, washed with ethanol containing a small amount of the ligand, dried over anhy. calcium chloride and analysed.

Complexes of the type NiL₂X₄ :—Bis-isoquinoline and bis-orthotolidine complexes were prepared by adding respective ligand (4 moles) to the anhy. nickel halide (1 mole) and then by gently heating when a clear solution was obtained. This was then kept in the cold for about 24 hours. The crystals separated were filtered, washed with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

For the preparation of the piperidine complexes, anhy. nickel halide (1 mole) and piperidine (4 moles) were mixed in a flask and kept on a boiling water bath for about 2 hours. The excess ligand was then decanted off and the solid product left was washed with ether and dried in vacuum over conc. sulphuric acid.

Ni(aniline)₂Cl₂ was obtained by the thermal decomposition of Ni(aniline)₄Cl₂ at 160°.

Complex of the type NiLX₄ :—Ni (Pyridine) (CNS)₂ was isolated by the thermal decomposition of the tetraligated complex as reported².

Ni(quinaldine)Cl₂—Nickel chloride hexahydrate (3 gms.) was first heated in presence of dry HCl gas at 110°C until it became golden yellow in colour. It was then refluxed for three hours with distilled quinaldine (10 gms.) and then cooled. The crystals obtained were filtered and washed repeatedly with chloroform till they became clear light yellow in colour. Found—Ni, 21.49%; Cl, 26.03%; C, 44.10%; H, 3.29%; N, 5.12%; Calculated—Ni, 21.52%; Cl, 26.04%; C, 44.00%; H, 3.30%; N, 5.13%.

Magnetic susceptibility and spectrophotometric measurements.—Magnetic measurements of the complexes at room temperature were made by the Gouy method, with mercury tetra-thiocyanato-cobaltate as the standard.

The absorption spectra of the complexes in chloroform were measured in a Hilger U-V Spectrophotometer over the range 350 to 1000 m μ . Glass cells with 10 mm. light path were used.

Conductivity measurement.—Conductivities in nitrobenzene were measured by Mullard conductivity bridge type E7566/2.

Reflectance spectra.—Beckman DU Spectrophotometer with reflectance attachment was used to record the reflectance spectra of the complexes; reference being barium sulphate for complexes marked (*) and magnesium carbonate for that marked (+).

Solvents.—The G.R. grade chloroform was distilled and the middle fractions were collected over anhy. calcium chloride.

The nitrobenzene was distilled at a reduced pressure and the middle fractions were used for conductivity study.

The authors are indebted to Mr. Barnard Dusonchet of Cyanamide European Research Institute, Coligny, Geneva and to Dr. A. K. Banerjee of Chemistry Department, Florida State University, Tallahassee, U.S.A., for their kindly recording the reflectance spectra.

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Received July, 22, 1966.